

INVESTIGATION OF A COST-EFFECTIVE SYSTEM FOR ON-LINE FLOW MONITORING AND QUALITY CONTROL IN RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates a fast method for flow monitoring and control during RTM processes. The approach is based on a smart combination of flow modeling and experimental data from few pressure transducers embedded in the mold. A sensing system, equipped with only 3 cavity pressure sensors, was developed to monitor injections into two-dimensional cavities with area up to 450 x 230 mm. A good agreement between real and estimated flow fronts was observed during experimental tests with single and dual scale fabrics, confirming that accurate monitoring was possible with a limited number of sensors and, thus, in a cost-effective way. The experimental campaign also proved that the approach could be used for mapping the permeability distribution and even preventing fiber wash-out through a computer-controlled pressure regulator added to the system. Furthermore, the combination of the sensors and the regulator enabled the control of injection parameters such as the flow rate during the impregnation. This allowed keeping the average flow front velocity automatically within the range of values that ensure a minimum void content, regardless of actual changes of permeability or cavity cross-section. The obtained results indicate that such a system can be prospectively applied to assess and control the quality of composite parts in the course of the production.

1 INTRODUCTION

Liquid Composite Molding (LCM) processes, like Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) and its variants, are increasingly used techniques for both high- and low-volume production of composite structures [1, 2]. In particular, Resin Transfer Molding is characterized by a liquid resin injection into a fibrous preform in a closed rigid mold and offers numerous advantages to the manufacturers. Nevertheless, the production of parts is very sensitive to unavoidable variations in the resin flow pattern during the injection. In order to ensure a standard laminate quality and minimize the final void content, it is thus important to control the preform impregnation through a suitable sensing system. This system should allow on-line flow front tracking and control in an accurate and cost-effective manner.

Several sensing technologies have been developed for applications in composite manufacturing in the past years [2-4]. Among those, pressure transducers are considerably advantageous because they are easy to use and applicable with the usual RTM processing conditions and materials. Furthermore, they give more data than just a 0/1 response for spotting the absence/presence of resin at the sensor location. As a matter of fact, those sensors allow tracking the resin flow and the determining textile permeability beyond their positions in the cavity [5-7]. It is, therefore, possible to use only few of them to monitor the flow front over a relatively large area, bringing remarkable benefits in terms of cost optimization. However, this can be done if the pressure data are combined to algorithms or models, which integrate the sensor information with the knowledge of equations governing the impregnation process (e.g., Darcy's law and continuity equation), in order to describe the relationships among resin pressure, velocity, preform permeability and other physical quantities or material parameters.

In previous works [5, 7], we have proposed a combined experimental-numerical approach to estimate flow front profiles in two-dimensional (2D) cavity geometries. The approach consists of

associating the pressures measured at discrete sensor points to the advancement of the flow front along defined paths, called flow paths. At each time step, the single pressure values from a small number of sensors are compared to numerical calculations of the pressure distribution in an optimization scheme. Minimizing the difference between measured and calculated pressures at the sensor points allows assessing the flow front positions on each flow path (one per sensor) and, hence, drawing the whole front profile by interpolating the flow front points on the paths. The methodology provides accurate flow front estimations even in complex 2D shapes, but the results depended on the sensor arrangement, on the knowledge of permeability variations within the cavity and on the physical time allowed for numerical calculations and optimizations of the computed pressure values [8]. For this reason, another approach has been devised [9] considering the historical data of pressure instead of only the values at a given impregnation time, in order to obtain information on unknown permeability distributions besides tracking the flow front. The approach, which was based on an analytical model for flow through porous media, focuses on rectilinear or one-dimensional injections and returns accurate flow front and permeability estimations in real time during the injections. Its potential for efficient permeability characterization as a function of FVC has been also demonstrated [10].

The present study proposes an extension of the aforementioned methodology to two-dimensional cases, including curved flow paths, flows around inserts and changes of the cross-section in planar cavity shapes. The new methodology does not rely upon computationally expensive optimizations and numerical calculations, because it combines data from few pressure sensors – strategically positioned in the mold – to a flow model exploiting the conservation of the resin flux through different zones of the preform. A priori knowledge of the permeability distribution along the flow paths is not required and such a distribution could be actually mapped during the injection. This work focuses on flow monitoring, but a preliminary investigation of permeability mapping is here also presented. The method can be further enhanced to control the injection pressure and, thus, the flow rate during the impregnation by using a computer-controlled pressure regulator connected to the sensing system. As a result, the whole system can be used to ensure that the flow front is progressing with a defined average velocity that reduces the formation of voids. In addition, the pressure regulator can be used to keep the injection pressure below a set limit that would trigger a fiber wash-out.

In the following section, the methodology is explained giving the basic equations developed to estimate the flow front positions along the flow paths. Based on the methodology, a lab-scale monitoring system equipped with three pressure sensors in the cavity was built and used to validate the approach. Information on the set-up, procedure and materials employed for the experimental validation is given in section 3. The results of the tests – including flow front monitoring, permeability mapping, wash-out prevention and flow front velocity control – are discussed in section 4. The last section summarizes the conclusions.

2 METHODOLOGY

The approach is initially presented with reference to Fig. 1, where a single cavity sensor is used, and then the discussion is extended to a generic 2D cavity such as the example of Fig. 2. The pressure sensor in Fig. 1 has x -coordinate x_s and the corresponding measured pressure is p_s . The cavity width W in the example of Fig. 1 varies with the position on the flow path, which coincides with the injection direction. Let μ denote the shape factor, defined as:

$$\mu = \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

If μ is small enough ($|\mu| \ll 1$) and the textile permeability variations perpendicular to the flow paths are negligible, then the flow front advances by approximately parallel straight lines toward the outlet (flow velocity components orthogonal to the flow path can be neglected). Such an assumption is verified by Cai [11] for $|\mu| \leq 0.25$. In this case, the amount of resin flowing is constant through any cross-section orthogonal to the path (injection direction) at each impregnation time t . Using Darcy's law, it is possible to derive the following equation:

$$\int_{x_s}^{x_f} c_s W(x) dx = \int_{t_s}^t (p_{in}(\tau) - p_s(\tau)) d\tau \quad (2)$$

where x_f is the flow front position, t_s is the time at which the resin arrives at the sensor, p_{in} is the injection pressure and c_s is a factor including constant parameters:

$$c_s = \frac{\eta \varphi (x_s - x_{in})}{K_s W_s} \quad (3)$$

in which η is the resin viscosity, φ the porosity (complementary to the fiber volume content), x_{in} the inlet position, W_s the width at x_s and K_s the permeability between x_{in} and x_s . If the initial permeability K_s is not known before the injection, it can be evaluated from t_s [9]. From equation (2), the flow front positions can be obtained at any time using a simple minimization technique – namely finding out the value of the variable ξ (between the positions of the sensor x_s and the outlet x_{out}), which minimize the objective function in the following equation:

$$x_f(t) = \arg \min_{x_s \leq \xi \leq x_{out}} \left(\left| \int_{x_s}^{\xi} c_s W(x) dx - \int_{t_s}^t (p_{in}(\tau) - p_s(\tau)) d\tau \right| \right) \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: Sketch of a two-dimensional cavity with variable cross-section. A single cavity sensor with linear flow path is considered in this exemplary geometry.

This procedure can be extended to more complex 2D cavities (Fig. 2) and to the use of multiple sensors. As in [5], a flow path is defined for each sensor and the cavity is ideally divided into different flow channels (one per flow path). For each channel, the flow front position l_f along the corresponding flow path is obtained from the following equation, which adapts the above equation (4) to the curvilinear l -axis of the path:

$$l_f(t) = \arg \min_{l_s \leq \xi \leq l_{out}} \left(\left| \int_{l_s}^{\xi} c_s w(l) dl - \int_{t_s}^t (p_{in}(\tau) - p_s(\tau)) d\tau \right| \right) \quad (5)$$

where l_s and l_{out} are respectively the positions of the sensor and the outlet on the l -axis and w is the varying width of the flow channel under consideration (perpendicular to the path contained by the channel). At each impregnation time, the sensor data are, therefore, used to determine the flow front positions along the flow paths and, then, such positions are interpolated to approximate the whole flow front line. Note that the accuracy of the flow front estimation depends on the arrangement of the sensor, the paths and the flow channels, into which the cavity is divided. Those parameters should be carefully designed for each mold shape, in order to respect the above mentioned assumptions (for example, the shape factor should be limited to a maximum value, below which the flow velocity components orthogonal to the flow paths are negligible).

Figure 2: Sketch of a cavity with fender-like geometry used as a reference test case in the experiments.

The approach can be further enhanced to map the permeability distribution along the flow paths. For this scope, the procedure illustrated in [9], adequately modified including the effects of a variable cross-section, can be applied using the estimated flow front positions as input. Note, however, that strong permeability variations among adjacent channels (as well as other possible effects that induce substantial flow velocity components orthogonal to the paths) may cause erroneous permeability reconstructions and, thus, several sensors all over the cavity as in [12] may be required to get acceptable results. Finally, it is worth pointing out that an external control of the injection pressure p_{in} in equation (5) allows adjusting the flow front positions and velocity. This fact can be advantageously used to establish a procedure of flow rate and quality control, as it is illustrated in the next sections.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

The methodology was validated through tests with textiles of glass fibers: a random mat and a plain weave fabric. They represented a single scale and dual scale porous media respectively. The random mat was supplied by Suter Kunststoffe AG (ID number 192.0812), while the woven fabric by Tissa Glasweberei AG (ID number 850.0470.01.1240). The used test liquid was Bluesil Oil 47 V100, by Bluestar Silicones France SAS. It was injected at approximately 1 bar at room temperature (the fluid viscosity was 0.1 Pa·s at 25 °C). The test rig used in [8, 10] was employed to test the methodology. Three pressure transducers (cavity sensors) were embedded in the mold in addition to the inlet sensor. The sensors were Relative Pressure Transmitters type 680, by Huba Control AG, as in [7, 10]. The pressure signals were read by a data acquisition module ADAM-6017, by Advantech Co. Ltd., and sent to a workstation for flow front monitoring in real time during the injection. The mold had a glass cover in order to take snapshots of the flow front progression and compare them to the flow front profiles estimated by the pressure sensors for validation purposes.

The fender-like shape in Fig. 2, with the indicated cavity sensor positions, was considered as a reference test case. The cavity had thickness of 2.9 mm, length of 450 mm and width of 230 mm (in some tests with rectangular preforms, a length of 225 mm or a width of 150 mm was also used). The typical number of layers employed in the tests was 10 for the random mat (corresponding to a nominal fiber volume content of 20 %) and 7 for the woven fabric (nominal fiber volume content of 44 %), unless otherwise specified in the figures of the next section.

For the experiments of flow control, a Proportional Pressure Regulator type VPPE (ID number 557771), by Festo AG, was installed at the inlet air pressure line. The regulator was controlled through a NI CompactDAQ with module NI 9236 in order to modify the injection pressure according to the input given by the main program in the workstation. A feedback control mechanism as in [7] was implemented: the flow front velocity was evaluated by the estimated flow front positions over time; if the velocity was outside a given range of values, the injection pressure was changed accordingly in a feedback loop. This mechanism was as well used to avoid fiber wash-out: if the injection pressure was close to an experimentally determined limit, at which the wash-out is likely to occur, the regulator at the inlet was activated to decrease the pressure. In this way, the injection could be safely conducted at the maximum pressure values, which do not cause a fiber wash-out. Note that the limit for the occurrence of fiber wash-out may vary depending on the flow front position. During the injection, the impregnated region increases and the dry region reduces; this can change the friction coefficient between the mold and the preform and, thus, the resistance of the same preform to the hydrodynamic forces inducing the wash-out. Since the flow front is monitored in real time, such mechanism for wash-out prevention is easily adaptable to varying limits and constraints for the injection pressure.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation and the discussion of the experimental results are distributed in the following four subsections depending on the purpose of the experiments.

4.1 Flow front monitoring

Figure 3: Flow monitoring during the impregnation of a preform of random mat.

Figure 4: Flow monitoring during the impregnation of a preform of woven fabric.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the results of the on-line flow monitoring in the cavity with fender-like geometry for the random mat and woven fabric respectively. In both cases, accurate flow front estimations were obtained using the data from only three cavity sensors with the proposed methodology. The biggest deviations between estimated and real flow fronts were observed around the curved edge of the cavity.

4.2 Permeability mapping

Assessment of permeability values in the various corners of a preform is a useful tool both for obtaining information on the flow pattern and for evaluating the product quality. As a matter of fact, textile permeability depends on the fiber volume content, which sets the mechanical properties of composite laminates (for example, using the rule of mixture). Thus, mapping the permeability during the injection would allow establishing on-line procedures of quality assessment for each manufactured part, because estimated maps of fiber volume content and mechanical properties can be ideally drawn knowing the permeability distribution [7]. Defective parts would be directly identified in the course of the production. In Fig. 5, the mapped permeability distribution in a cavity with fender-like geometry is illustrated. The preform was entirely made up of 9 layers of random mat, except from a zone where 11 layers were laid up. It is noticeable that, in the zone of 11 layers, lower permeability values were observed from the data of all three sensors. The results are overall acceptable and encouraging, but the approach requires still refinements, especially in the case of high shape factor and flow channels with big curvatures.

Figure 5: Estimated permeability distribution of a preform of random mat with varying number of textile layers in a cavity with fender-like geometry.

4.3 Wash-out prevention

The presented approach enabled the prevention of fiber wash-out or, more generally, textile deformations due to hydrodynamic forces by concurrent flow monitoring and injection pressure regulation. The feasibility of the pressure control was proved with long and short rectangular preforms of random mat with low fiber volume contents. Fig. 6 shows the curve of injection pressure in a case where the wash-out was avoided. As soon as the injection reached a set limit line, above which the wash-out was expected, the control was started in order to reduce the injection pressure below a lower line with a safety margin than the upper limit. As stated in section 3, the approach gives the freedom to link the limit lines to parameter measurable during the injections like the flow front positions.

Figure 6: Controlled injection pressure (solid line) during an experiment without wash-out.

4.4 Flow front velocity control

Figure 7: Flow front velocity control experiments in rectangular mold cavity.

Injection with controlled flow front velocity allows minimizing the total void content in the composite parts and thus improving the final quality [12]. For this reason, a simple and effective flow control procedure was established to integrate the developed monitoring system as illustrated above. The experiments here presented were performed to test the feasibility of the feedback mechanism for keeping the flow velocity automatically performed within a defined range of values. Fig. 7 shows the results of two experiments with the two tested textiles in rectangular mold geometry, using only one cavity sensor. In both cases, the average flow front velocity was kept between 2.5 and 3.5 mm/s (the selected target range of values). Moreover, Fig. 8 shows that the flow control mechanism was successful applied also in the case of spatially varying textile layers in the preform – namely, varying fiber volume content and non-uniform preform permeability – and non-rectangular mold geometry.

Figure 8: Flow front velocity control experiments with random mat with non-uniform permeability and non-rectangular mold cavity (the fender-like geometry configuration of Fig. 2 was tested).

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes a combined experimental–numerical methodology for monitoring and control RTM processes. The methodology relies upon a small number of pressure sensors to monitor two-dimensional resin injections. In addition, the sensing system can be easily enhanced with a pressure regulator at the inlet that enables the control of the injection pressure or the flow rate (and thus the flow front velocity) for improving the laminate quality during the manufacturing of each part. Based on this methodology, a cost-effective system was developed for experimental testing. The results show that the system was able to provide accurate flow front monitoring, permeability mapping, wash-out prevention and flow front velocity control. Future research should address the improvement of the

methodology with particular reference to refined schemes for on-line permeability estimations and flow control, considering more complex injection cases than the one analyzed in this study.

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